

CHEMICAL DISPOSITION OF ZINC OXIDE USE IN LIGHT EMITTING DIODES AND PHOTO DETECTORS

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Abstract

Zinc Oxide is a potential candidate for application in optoelectronics emitting blue to ultraviolet light. The compound bears fundamental advantages, including 3.37 eV wide bandgap, 60 meV large exciton binding energy, and 320 cm room temperature high optical gain. The mixture also has luminescent properties extensively researched for thin film, bulk, and nanostructure samples prepared through a range of methods and doped with various impurities. 1D semiconducting zinc oxide nanostructures have exceptional photoelectric features such as sub-wavelength, many light confinement, and ultrahigh intrinsic photoelectric gain. These Zinc Oxide nanowires do not have grain boundaries; they have a higher phase purity, and long-distance order in comparison with the polycrystalline thin films, properties that make them suitable transport carriers for advanced optoelectronic devices. The nanowires' properties, including photoconductive gains, light emission, and excellent optical absorption that improve the performance of solar cells. Other properties include sensors, light-emitting diodes (LED), nanogenerators, and field-effect transistors. This research proposal looks into how to fabricate one-dimensional Zinc Oxide nanostructures through chemical vapor deposition for application in optoelectronic devices.

Keywords: Zinc Oxide, Light-emitting diode, photodetector, one-dimensional nanostructure.

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Introduction

One dimensional nanomaterial has small sizes that earn them unique optical, electrical, chemical, and mechanical properties making them suitable for use in nanotechnology and nanoscience. Such features as multiple array light confinement and ultrahigh intrinsic photoelectric gain make one dimension Zinc Oxide an excellent material for use in nanotechnology. Several studies have studied materials made of Zinc Oxide for the construction of advanced optoelectronic devices, which have improved efficiency. The excellent properties of one-dimensional Zinc Oxide nanomaterials earn it the potential for use as nano-structured systems basic unit. Nanostructures made developed from one-dimensional Zinc Oxide include nanowires, nanotubes, nanorods, and nanobelts (Wang, Zhao, Xu, Kong, and Gong, 2011). The application requirements in these structures make one-dimensional Zinc Oxide ideal for use in providing an ideal medium in the construction of optoelectronic devices. The compound has excellent properties like high mobility carrier transport, efficient confinement of light, and emission of light. Thus, one dimension Zinc Oxide nanowires are used in devices that for use in the discharge of light, photon detection, and sensing of biochemicals. The nanowire-like structures are also used in the physical studies that investigate carrier transport, confinement of light, and loss of energy behaviors of one dimension objects. Meaning one-dimensional zinc oxide is favorable for low-dimensional system underlying phenomena extermination and construction of new high-performance nanodevice types.

Zinc oxide is a member of the II-IV family with such features as 3.37 eV wide direct bandgap, 60 meV room temperature large exciton binding energy, and favorable properties for use in nanomaterial production. Zinc oxide materials can potentially be applied in optical waveguides, solid-state lighting, transparent conductive films, varistors, and gas sensors (Yi,

Wang, and Park, 2005). The fact that zinc oxide has a wide bandgap means that it can be used in ultraviolet spectral range or blue emitting solid-state optoelectronics such as lasers. Besides, its feature of large exciton binding energy makes it an excellent candidate for use in the display of efficient excitonic emission even at room temperature.

Literature Review

Wang (2004) presents several methods developed that one dimension zinc oxide nanomaterials can be fabricated. These include molecular beam epitaxy, vapor transport, chemical vapor deposition, electrodeposition, hydrothermal reaction, and pulsed laser deposition. The researcher states that samples of Si, quartz, and sapphire can be obtained using any of these methods which have their own unique weaknesses and strengths. The use of a gas vapor method in the fabrication of high-quality single-crystalline zinc oxide nanostructures requires high temperatures between 450-1000 degrees centigrade. The technique has such flaws as poor uniformity of samples, low product yield, and narrow choice of substrates. In the preparation of one dimension nanomaterials for the low cost, large-area manufacturing compatibility, and controllability, solution processing is the most suitable method.

Yi, Wang, and Park, (2005) compared other nanomaterials with one dimension and argues that zinc oxide possesses three advantages, including the piezoelectric effect semiconductivity forming the foundation for electric mechanical coupling inverters and sensors. It also has relatively high biosecurity and biocompatibility, making it suitable for use in medicine. One dimension Zinc oxide has the most extensive known nanostructure range, including nanotubes, nanobelts, nanotrees, nanoplates, nanorods, nanospheres, nanowires, nanoleaves, and nanosail. Others include zinc-oxide tetrapods, porous array, microrod/microwire, matrix, and 3D network nanostructures, which have also been obtained.

Presently, many researchers focus on the construction of devices based on zinc oxide nanomaterials, meaning that new tools are under development, including the room temperature lesser, photodetectors, light-emitting diodes, transistors, and sensors. The devices show high performance than other devices that use thin films and bulk materials due to the fact that they contain one dimension zinc oxide materials. The fact that these devices developed forms the use of one dimension zinc oxide nanomaterials shows that it has a immense prospective for use in many fields.

Wang, Zhao, Xu, Kong, and Gong, (2011) in an article reviewed various zinc oxide nanostructures using solid vapor phase, nanoresonators, and field-effect transistors. Yi, Wang, and Park (2005) studied the fabrication methods of fabricating and doping zinc oxide nanorods and discussed the properties associated with them, such as luminescence, electron transport, field emission, and other applications. The researchers also reviewed the zinc oxide nanostructures fabricated using the dop and alloy method, wet chemical methods, used in catalysis, patterned growth, sensing, optoelectronics, and surface modification. The review looks mainly into the one-dimension zinc-oxide nanostructures growth conditions and achievement of photodetectors and LEDs, based on one dimension zinc oxide and the promising methods of improving the performance of these devices.

Methodology

In the synthesis of one dimension nanostructures, the study used Chemical Vapor Deposition. The process uses zinc oxide powder, zinc powder, and another zinc compound as the main requirements after vaporization, reduction/oxidation, and combination/decomposition. The growth process is conducted in a furnace made of a horizontal tube consisting of a control system, gas supply, horizontal tube heater, and quartz, or an alumina tube. Fabricating one-

dimensional zinc oxide is affected by the parameters of synthesis, including temperature, substrate and source temperature growth, pressure, substrate-source distance, the rate of heating, species of the gas and the rate of flow, the carrier gas, the diameter of the tubes.

The preparation of ZnO-Cu_xO core-shell nanowire arrays is carried out in two steps. The Nanowires are obtained by thermal oxidation in the oxidation 2 square centimeters of zinc foils are then cleaned in isopropyl alcohol and acetone for five minutes and rinsed using deionized water, nitrogen spray gun dried and then oxidized thermally. The zinc foils should be of 1mm thickness and a temperature of 500 degrees centigrade for a time of 12 hours.

In the second step, the zinc Oxide nanowires are enclosed in a thin Cu_xO layer by a radio frequency magnetron sputtering. A power of 100W is applied to the magnetron and the chamber pressure set at 5.4×10^{-3} mbar in a 9.6 purity Ar atmosphere. The copper target 2 inch diameter width and 0.125-inch thickness. Before the electronic device is fabricated, the prepared ZnO-Cu_xO core-shell nanowire arrays are, through ultrasonication, conveyed in ultrapure isopropyl alcohol. They will result in a suspension of ZnO-Cu_xO core-shell nanowires.

The vapor-liquid-solid process is commonly used for one-dimension zinc oxide nanostructure growth using Chemical vapor deposition. It needs the use of a catalyst like gold, cobalt, copper or tin. Liquid droplet is used as a gas-phase reactant adoption site until it is saturated and turns into a nucleation crystallization place. The thickness of the gold layer helps in controlling the width of the nanowire as well. In addition to the use of external catalysts, Zinc can function as catalyst in specific setting in the preparation of zinc oxide nanostructures.

Equipment

The Ti/Au (10/100 nm) on Si/SO₂ (50nm) metallic interdigitated electrodes substrates are fabricated through photolithography, thermal vacuum evaporation and RF magnetron

sputtering. Photolithography is made using an EVG 620 Mask Alignment System. The techniques of thin layer deposition are made using Tectra equipment. The ZnO-Cu_xO core-shell nanowire droplets are dipped onto substrate of Si/SiO₂ that contain Ti/Au electrodes. The Single of ZnO-Cu_xO core-shell radial heterojunction nanowires are joined using pt electrodes using electron beam lithography and magnetic sputtering. Fabrication process of electronic devices uses all the lithography equipment placed in a cleanroom facility.

Conclusion

One-dimension zinc oxide nanomaterials have considerable binding exciton energy, high carrier mobility, wide bandgap, and non-centrosymmetric structure necessary for the improvement of semiconductivity, photoexcitation, and piezoelectricity for development of highly efficient next-generation devices with intelligent features. Fabrication of nanomaterials can form the basis for the development of novel methods with improved performance for different uses. Such approaches as surface passivation, LPs, and piezo-phototronic effects can be used in the improvement of the performance of the devices. In light of the broad application potential of one-dimension zinc oxide nanomaterials, and their excellent performances, they can be used for smaller, faster, and colder electronics development. The use of zinc oxide nanomaterials has expanded over the years, together with the improvement of the performance of different electronic devices. Future research has to be on the development of new high-performance devices using one dimension of zinc oxide nanomaterials. One-dimension zinc

oxide nanomaterials will increasingly play a vital function security, nanoscience, nanotechnology, ICT, national defense, environmental protection, biomedicine, and energy fields with improvement of the preparation technology, increased research and continuous development of the performance of devices.

References

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